

beaker and diluted to about 125 ml. Required amount of 3N HCl is introduced to adjust the pH at 0.5 to 1.5 and 2.0 to 3.0 for gold and copper respectively. The solution is heated on a water bath and the reagent solution (0.5%, m/V, in 10% ethanol) is introduced dropwise with constant stirring. The precipitate, thus obtained, is digested for an hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible G4, washed with hot water to remove any adhering reagent and dried to a constant weight at 120°. The weights of the complexes multiplied by 0.46790 and 0.22078 give the weights of gold and copper respectively.

Determinations in the presence of Diverse ions :

The reagent is quite selective for the determination of Au(I) and Cu(II). The presence of alkali metals, alkaline earths, ammonium, Zn(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Cd(II), Pb(II), Bi(III), Tl(I), Th(IV), Zr(IV), Ce(IV) and other rare earths, VO(II), UO₂(II) and molybdate does not impair the determinations of Au(I) and Cu(II). Tungstate does not interfere with the determinations, however, the determinations were carried out at pH 3.0 in order to prevent the precipitation of tungstic acid. Au(I) is determined in the presence of Cu(II) by masking the latter with EDTA at pH 3.0.

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Synthesis of Dithiotetrathiazoline Diones

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THIAZOLINES and their derivatives have drawn the attention of scientists due to their prodigious range of activity¹. They are chiefly used as analgesics, nematocides, bactericides, fungicides, vulcanisation accelerators, etc. These compounds are also popular for their radio protective activities in the present day therapy.

A perusal of literature reveals that no work has been done on the reaction of chloranil with substituted dithiocarbamates.

In continuation to our work on pyrrocoline quinones^{2,3}, thiadiazolobenzimidazoles⁴, the present communication describes the synthesis of a series of new thiazoline diones by condensing chloranil with substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates. The products isolated were 3 : 7-disubstituted 2 : 6-dithio 1 : 3 : 5 : 7 tetrathiazoline 4 : 8 diones(I).

TABLE 1—3 : 7-DISUBSTITUTED 2 : 6-DITHIO 1 : 3 : 5 : 7-TETRATHIAZOLINE 4 : 8-DIONES

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Analysis		I. R. data
					Calcd.	Found	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	57	>350	C, 54.8 H, 2.2 N, 6.4	54.2 1.8 6.2	C=S 1185 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1610 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1660 cm ⁻¹
2.	p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	50	>350	C, 35.0 H, 1.9 N, 6.8	34.4 1.6 6.4	C=S 1210 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1605 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1665 cm ⁻¹
3.	o-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	45	327	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.1 2.7 5.6	C=S 1190 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1600 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1675 cm ⁻¹
4.	m-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	37	314	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.3 2.4 5.7	C=S 1180 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1625 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1685 cm ⁻¹
5.	p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	41	270 (decomp.)	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.0 2.7 5.5	C=S 1195 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1620 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1675 cm ⁻¹
6.	o-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	32	305	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.2 1.2 5.0	C=S 1190 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1605 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1665 cm ⁻¹
7.	m-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	41	>350	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.0 1.1 5.1	C=S 1230 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1610 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1680 cm ⁻¹
8.	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	37	319	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.3 1.8 4.8	C=S 1215 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1600 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1670 cm ⁻¹

Compound of the type (I) might also be active against fungi. Such compounds have $\text{N}-\overset{\text{I}}{\text{C}}=\text{S}$ group which is perhaps responsible for their fungicidal activity. All the compounds of this series gave characteristic red colour with conc. H_2SO_4 .

Experimental

All the melting points have been determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. The I.R. spectra were determined with a Perkin-Elmer infra-red model-577 using KBr disc.

The general procedure adopted for the preparation of thiazoline diones is as given below :

A mixture of chloranil (0.1 mole), substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates (0.2 mole), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.8 g) in ethanol (25 ml) were heated under reflux on a steam bath for about 6 hrs. The coloured solid was washed with water, sodium carbonate solution and then dried. It was recrystallised twice from DMF-ethanol. The purity of products was established by analyses and TLC. The analysis, m.p., I.R. data, etc., are given in Table 1.

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Melting of Nitrophenols and Nitrotoluenes

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VASUDEVAN and Beddoes¹ studied zone melted sample of *m*-nitrophenol (MNP) and established that it exists in two different crystal modifications. Also interesting properties were noted in the melt and supercooled regions. We report here the dilatometric data in these regions for *o*-*m*- and *p*-nitrophenols and *p*-nitrotoluene.

Experimental

The compounds were purified by methods described in the literature^{2,3}. The solids were subjected to repeated recrystallisation. MNP was further purified by zone-melting. IR spectra of the samples were recorded for purity check. Densities of the melts were determined by a pipette type of pycnometer⁴. Volume changes on melting and in the post melt region were measured in a specially designed dilatometer containing a weighed sample. All the trapped air was released by repeated melting and freezing under vacuum. Ultimately mercury was filled over the sample and its level served as reference. The dilatometer was placed in a thermostat for thermal equilibrium, the temperature being controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The cryoscopic constant K_f of the compounds under study was determined, using purified naphthalene as the solute.

Results and Discussion

The volume changes in the premelting, melting and post-melting regions up to 20° above the melting point were recorded.

The density (ρ) of the compounds above the melting point is linear with temperature (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Density of Nitrophenol Melts at Various Temperatures.

The ratio $\frac{d\rho}{dT}$ is in the expected range of $(8.0-9.0) \times 10^{-4}$. Bondi⁵ suggested that packing density (ρ^*) be defined by $\frac{\rho V_w}{M} = \frac{V_w}{V}$, where V_w is the van der Waal molar volume and V , the actual volume. This